

Mechanisms and Regulatory Implications of Oil Leakage into the Cabin Air Supply

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ABBREVIATIONS

AMC	Acceptable means of compliance
APU	Auxiliary power unit
CS	Certification standards
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FAR	Federal aviation regulations

ABSTRACT

There are certification and airworthiness requirements relevant to the provision of clean breathing air for the aircraft crew and passenger compartments. A Masters of Science (MSc) research degree,¹ was undertaken to assess whether there is any gap between the certification requirements for the provision of clean air in crew and passenger compartments, and the theoretical and practical implementation of the requirements using the bleed air system. Low level oil leakage into the aircraft cabin in normal flight operations is a function of the design of the engine lubricating system and bleed air systems, both utilizing pressurized air as required. The use of the bleed air system to supply breathing air has regulatory implications that require changes to be implemented.

INTRODUCTION

There are extensive reports regarding concerns about contamination of the aircraft bleed air supply (fume

events) extending back to the early 1950s. This coincided with the introduction of synthetic jet oils that replaced mineral oils and the introduction of higher performing, higher temperature and pressure turbine engines.² Varying types of reports have continued to the present day such as military, airline, manufacturer and crew reports. Furthermore, there have been airworthiness directives, regulator initiatives, legal and insurance claims, scientific committee studies, published literature and media reports. The 'vast majority' of fume events are associated with an abnormal leakage of engine or auxiliary power unit (APU) oil.³ Frequency of exposure to engine oils, are suggested to range from rare and infrequent to frequent with seals leaking as a normal function of their design and operation, whilst oil seals can be reliant upon compressed air for their sealing functionality. However, under-reporting is common and impairment has been reported in around 30% of the reported events. Exposure to a range of hazardous substances and pyrolysis by-products, from engine oils and hydraulic and deicing fluids contaminating the aircraft air supply, is increasingly recognized as potentially adversely impacting flight safety. Despite no real time monitoring to detect compressor bleed air contamination, a growing number of studies have confirmed the presence of low levels of oil substances in the air supply system in normal operations between 25% and 100% of flights. While the significance of exposure continues to be questioned, an increasing number of global initiatives continue to be undertaken.

There are two key ways in which oil leakage outside of the bearing chamber is reported to occur. Outside the specialist engineering and air/oil sealing community, the wider aviation industry community commonly suggests oil leakage occurs only as a result of seal failure or operational deficiencies, such as seal wear or oil overfilling and as such is very rare. The alternative view is that oil seal leakage occurs at low levels during normal phases of flight, indicating that all engines leak low levels of oil from the bearings through the seals during transient power changes and while the engines are still achieving optimum temperatures and pressures. The specialist sealing and engineering community tend to support

the later view, however their views are not commonly reported.

The lower level leakage has generally been viewed as normal and safe, associated with minor discomfort only, with the larger events such as seal bearing failure or wear possibly affecting occupant health or flight safety.⁴

There are clear regulatory standards and guidelines related to the aircraft air quality and differing views as to how the air can become degraded. It was therefore decided to raise a research question addressing oil leakage out of the bearing chamber to determine if this was an occasional maintenance or failure issue or a function of normal engine operation.

The aim of this work was to assess if there is any gap between aircraft certification requirements for the clean air in crew and passenger compartments of transport aircraft using the bleed air system and the theoretical and practical implementation of the requirements.

METHODS

The research consisted of three elements:

1. A review of the certification regulations, standards and guidance/compliance material;
2. Assessment of the documented understanding of bleed air contamination of the aircraft cabin air supply;
3. Research addressing the real-world implementation of the certification requirements requiring clean bleed air.

In order to understand the practical real-world implementation of the requirements using the bleed air system, two separate interview processes were utilized:

1. Semi structured interview undertaken with European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) and Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) airframe and engine/APU airworthiness departments about the process

by which they certify and ensure clean aircraft air requirements are met with the use of bleed air.

2. Semi structured interviews undertaken with ten experienced aviation engineering professionals and two seal supplier experts about their professional judgement on how oil may leak past oil-bearing seals into the air supply under various flight operational conditions.

RESULTS

Key relevant airworthiness certification standards/regulations and guidance/compliance material relate to the following areas. A complete list can be found in the original research.¹

Airframe level

- CS/FAR 25.1309 – Equipment and systems design ‘hazardous’ and ‘major’ failure conditions must be extremely remote and remote respectively under the EU certification standards (CS). The acceptable means of compliance (AMC), are an established way of meeting the CS standards. The AMC establish that ‘hazardous’ failure conditions occur not more than 1×10^{-7} /flight hour (/fh) or a few times during the total life of all the aeroplanes of type. These include failure conditions causing pilots to be unable to be relied upon to perform their jobs accurately or completely or for a few other occupants to sustain serious injury. AMC ‘major’ failure conditions should not occur more than 1×10^{-5} /fh and are unlikely to occur to each aeroplane but may occur several times during the total life of a number of aircraft of type. These include impaired crew efficiency, discomfort to the pilots and physical distress or injuries to other occupants. The US federal aviation regulations (FAR) are little different apart from terminology based on major failure conditions reducing the capability of the crew to cope with adverse conditions to being improbable ($\leq 1 \times 10^{-5}$ – $> 1 \times 10^{-9}$ /fh). Minor or probable failure conditions listed under the EU AMC are those occurring above 1×10^{-5} /fh causing a slight increase in crew workload or some inconvenience to

occupants.

- CS and FAR 25.831 relate to the airworthiness ventilation and heating for the cabin. They require that each crew compartment has enough fresh air enabling crew to perform their duties without undue discomfort or fatigue. The FAR is very similar but requires a sufficient amount of uncontaminated air and references reasonable passenger comfort. Crew and passenger compartments must be free of harmful or hazardous concentrations of gases or vapours. Only carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), ozone (O₃) levels and fresh airflow rates are listed.
- Warning systems must be provided to alert the crew to unsafe system operating conditions and to enable them to take corrective action under FAR and CS 25.1309C.
- An unsafe condition includes events that occur more frequently than the safety objectives allow, or that may reduce the ability of the crew to cope with adverse operating conditions, impair crew efficiency or cause discomfort/injuries to occupants EASA AMC 21. A.3Bb
- There are various other voluntary standards or recommended practices that have been published over the years.

Engine level

- CS E (engine) 510 and CS APU 210 engines and APU safety analysis require that 'hazardous' engine/APU effects are extremely remote, 10^{-7}/engine flight hour (/efh) or APU operating hour (APU o/h) up to 10^{-9}/efh. This includes toxic products in the engine or APU bleed air intended for the cabin sufficient to incapacitate crew or passengers. Degradation of oil leaking into the compressor airflow is listed as such toxic products under the AMC. The safety analysis must include compressor bleed air systems. 'Major' engine/APU effects must not be greater than remote (10^{-5}/efh or APU o/h) under the CS. The AMC 'major effects' includes toxic products in the bleed air sufficient to degrade crew performance. The US FAR, CFR 14 33.75 engine safety analysis

and related guidance material is very similar. A US APU Technical Standing Order (TSO- C77b) requires that failures do not generate an unacceptable concentration of toxic products in the bleed air.

In dealing with such low probabilities, absolute proof is not possible with reliance placed on good engineering judgment, previous experience, sound design & test philosophies.

- CS E-690 requires contamination or purity tests of the bleed air when it is directly used in the cabin and an analysis of defects that could cause this to occur.

Oil sealing

Around 25% of the engine core airflow is extracted and utilized to supply engine internal air and various aircraft systems. This secondary air, also known as bleed air is primarily tapped off the compressor and used for cooling the engine, and accessory components, bearing chamber oil cooling and sealing, control of turbine tip clearances, cavity ventilation bearing load controls, cabin pressurization, ventilation, anti-icing and other services. The extracted secondary/bleed air is controlled and minimized as it reduces power and efficiency of the engine. To do this a number of oil and air seals are required.

A recirculatory oil system provides oil under high pressure for various purposes including lubrication, cooling and sealing. The minimum amount of oil performs these duties taking into account the permissible consumption of oil, usually around 0.1-0.5 US quarts per engine per hour.

Main shaft bearings grouped together in bearing chambers require a continuous supply and removal of oil. Pressurized air from the compressor is used to prevent oil leaking through the bearing seals and to cool and ventilate the bearing sumps. Pressurized air is used to maintain the bearing compartment at a lower pressure than the surroundings, causing an inward flow and preventing an outward leak. Oil seals have various functions including to prevent moisture and dirt entering the chamber, prevent outward leakage of oil (prevents fumes in cabin, fires, loss of performance), control

air leakage in (improves performance) and reduce oil consumption.

There was high awareness of oil contamination of the bleed air supply in the 1950s and early 1960s, however the desire to reduce the costs associated with an extra compressor for the air supply, bleed air was accepted as being of similar quality to outside air. This led to the acceptance of using bleed air to supply the ventilation air required for the cabin.

There are various factors affecting seals. All dynamic seals are designed to leak. How much they leak depends on many factors including the style / type of seal, the hydrodynamic effects; the balance ratio or tooth patterns, the variabilities of the lubricating regime, general operating conditions (speed, temperatures and pressures), wear and distortion.

There are two main types of seals used in aero engines:

Labyrinth seals or non-contacting clearance seals operate with tight clearances. The controlled leakage of air or liquid over restrictions reduces pressure over the seal. Fluid can flow in either direction depending on pressure, momentum and design. Performance deteriorates with time, wear and change in operating conditions, with clearances increasing for example with 'rubs'. Labyrinths are renowned for being low cost and simple.

Mechanical (face, positive contact) carbon seals operate with a micro seal face separation (typically 0.25-1 μm), providing low (non-visible) leakage. The oil film in the face separation is a factor of the hydrodynamics effects acting on the seal, and is a designed compromise between being thick enough to provide lubrication and long seal life, but as thin as possible to minimize leakage. Pressure and temperature distortion during operation can impact the parallelism of the flat seal faces, thereby reducing or increasing leakage. Seal face material condition or surface roughness can influence the oil film condition, while gradual wear of the sealing faces will occur. This type of seal is more complex and expensive.

Common assumptions regarding oil leakage include:

1. Higher pressure in the gas path than in the bearing chamber will keep the oil in the bearing chamber;
2. Seals leak only when a failure occurs;
3. Reverse pressures are to be avoided so as to prevent leakage.

However, oil may flow both with and against the positive pressure gradient with both types of seals. Positive pressure gradients are difficult to attain at near ambient pressures that are used in sealing bearing chambers. Reverse pressures over the seals, unless designed for, allow oil to flow in the opposite direction with both types of seals. Labyrinths operate with a clearance while mechanical face seals allow the face to open up. All dynamic seals will leak, with seals designed to limit leakage or emissions.

Upon closer review, specialist sealing and aero industry awareness of oil seal leakage is well established. Manufacturers have differing views on which seals offer greater advantages and disadvantages, with sealing technology in this industry suggested to not have kept pace with other major engine component advances.⁵ However advancement in sealing technology are being developed, however these styles of conventional seals will be around for a long while.⁶

Research

The following responses were given as a result of the two interview studies undertaken. Full responses can be seen in the original research.⁷

Engineers

- Oil leakage from the bearing chamber can be both internal and external to the engine/APU. Leakage may be a part of the normal oil consumption out via the oil system breather or may enter the core airflow with the potential to enter the cabin bleed air.
- Leakage past the seals can occur as a function of the seal design as they are not an absolute design. Leakage occurs with changing pressure differentials,

thermal, axial and radial (mechanical) changes in engine structures; changes in engine speed and power and design parameters not taking account of all engine conditions. Operational factors such as seal wear, installation and maintenance can also affect leakage.

- Various phases of flight affect leakage such as changes in engine performance- changing pressure differentials and balances over the seals with differing transient engine power, application and ambient conditions affecting seal efficiency and leakage rates; mechanical variations in structures over the engine operating range and low power settings such as start, spool up, top of descent, descent.
- Both carbon face and labyrinth seals leak for varying reasons with some leakage inevitable as it is inherent in the design. Labyrinth seals rely more so on pressure differentials, while mechanical seals require lubrication between the sealing surfaces allowing for leakage across the faces, and are more subject to wear, and are temperature critical. Leakage occurs both with and against the pressure drop with both types of seals.
- There are no specific published limits for oil contamination and there are differing views on when action is required to be taken. Some regard action is required only if oil leakage is above permissible limits, while others regard low level leakage is part of the system design and fails to meet the published design requirements. Regulatory enforcement is regarded as a low priority with available standards ignored.
- Oil leakage is seen in two differing ways: oil leaving the intended areas, loss over the seals or resides in greater amounts than intended. Alternatively, leakage is seen as leakage above the permissible consumption limits and pressure differentials, with lower-level leakage or emissions ignored.
- Under-reporting of oil leakage is generally accepted as occurring.
- Mitigating oil leakage should be given high priority including improved maintenance, better designs, filtration, electric systems and real time monitoring.

Regulators

- With regards to engine/APU certification, there is no specific process that the manufacturers must follow to demonstrate compliance. Bleed air quality compliance under CS E510 and FAR 33.75 addresses hazardous engine effects, including toxic products, such as oil in the bleed air capable of incapacitating crew or passengers at an 'extremely remote' rate of $<10^{-7}$ - $>10^{-9}$ /efh. There are no specific regulatory limits provided, however EASA references SAE recommended practice (4418) as a means to demonstrate compliance. Bleed air purity testing is required under CS E 690 and CS APU 320, however no specific guidance is given, while the FAA lists oil leakage into the compressor airflow as a toxic product, with no further guidance given.
- With regards to the airframe certification, the regulators require enough fresh air or sufficient uncontaminated air to avoid discomfort, fatigue, a minimum airflow, with CO, CO₂ and O₃ considered only. The FAA requires more recent certification programs to address the National Research Council's (NRC) cabin air quality recommendations and to consider a range of other optional standards and guidelines and sources of data to show that incapacitation will not occur. EASA reports there is an interactive process between the regulator and the manufacturers, but provided no details.

DISCUSSION

Regulations, standards and guidance material related to cabin air quality exist which ought to be acceptable in demonstrating compliance. There are however limitations in the descriptive terminology and the presentation of the requirements between the standards and guidance material. This could enable the compliance requirements and AMC to be interpreted in a number of ways or with lesser priority. For example, the engine safety analysis standard refers to toxic products in the bleed air sufficient to incapacitate, while oil leakage into the airflow causing degraded crew performance is listed in the AMC non mandatory guidance material. This may well explain why a lesser focus is placed on oil causing impairment.

The specific details relating to what is considered toxic products sufficient to incapacitate or degrade performance, the air requirements not causing adverse effects or failing to refer to substances other than CO, CO₂ and O₃ and further details on warning systems are absent. This allows room for interpretation and failure to adhere to the standards and guidance material.

There is a clear discrepancy in the understanding of oil contamination of the bleed air supplied to the cabin. The general understanding within and outside the aviation industry, primarily supports leakage due to failed bearing seals, operational factors such as worn seals or overfilled oil reservoirs. There is a less well-known view that oil leaks at background levels as a function of the design using the pressurized bleed air system. The literature involving the seals and aero experts is not widely available, but clearly shows oil leakage at lower levels occurs. Pressurized compressor air is used to seal the bearing compartment, but is responsive to variations in engine operating conditions. Both types of commonly used bearing compartment seals⁷ allow low level oil leakage across the seal, with various operating factors effecting leakage levels further.

The engineering and sealing experts identified a variety of factors allowing low-level oil leakage to enter the compressor air and the bleed air system in normal flight including:

- Changes in pressures and balances during different engine operating and ambient conditions/transient performance changes reduce seal efficiency;
- Thermal, axial and radial changes in engine structures cause changes in gaps needing to be sealed over whole engine operating range;
- Low internal pressures at various phases of engine operation;
- Standards and designs modeled on steady state conditions, not transients;
- Seals are not an absolute design, enabling leakage;
- Seal wear/component degradation.

Based upon the responses given by the engineering and

seals experts and the regulators, there is a discrepancy between the design standards and their implementation using the bleed air system. 'Major' engine/APU effects should not occur greater than remote or 10⁻⁵/efh. Under the guidance material, these include oil leakage into the compressor airflow sufficient to degrade crew performance. The emphasis by the regulators is placed on the regulatory or standard component addressing 'hazardous' effects of toxic products able to cause incapacitation, while almost ignoring the guidance component and major effects. Airframe regulations/standards do not allow failure conditions which reduce the ability of the crew to cope with adverse operating conditions to be more than improbable or 'major'/remote. Under the guidance material, these include impairment to crew efficiency, discomfort to flight crew or physical distress to other occupants and should not be more frequent than 1x10⁻⁵/fh. Such failure conditions may occur several times during the total life of a number of airplanes of type, but unlikely to occur to each airplane. The literature associates the lubricants and their substances with adverse effects.⁸⁻¹⁵ These can be expected to occur more frequently than remotely or improbably (10⁻⁵/ flight hour, engine or APU flight hour), based on 1) the design; 2) hazard recognition under the various chemical databases and literature and 3) frequency reported. Impaired crew efficiency or degraded crew performance can and is expected to occur with exposures. The frequency based on the design meets the definition of 'probable' (10⁻³-10⁻⁵) or above which allow no adverse effects on the flight crew or discomfort to others only through to no effect on flight crew or inconvenience on others only. Exposure to oils via the bleed air system does not meet this. Major effects are expected which must be improbable or remote, yet they are probable and not infrequent.

CS 25.831 requires the air supply to have sufficient fresh or uncontaminated air so as to not cause undue discomfort or fatigue and must be free of harmful or hazardous concentrations of gasses or vapors. However adverse effects are expected and occurring. The regulator emphasis is placed on the ventilation rates and CO, CO₂, while ignoring the discomfort component and

all other chemical substances. More recently, reliance on selected industry actions, studies and standards have been regarded as acceptable means of compliance.

The lack of detection systems and warning indicators to identify oil fumes in flight fails to meet CS/FAR 25.1309C addressing unsafe system operating conditions. There are conflicting views on how low-level oil leakage in normal operations is regarded and it is clear the problem remains unaddressed. However, the system design enabling oil leakage as a part of its function, cannot meet the stipulated airworthiness requirements.

CONCLUSIONS

Low-level leakage of oil fumes containing hazardous and harmful substances occurs in normal flight via the aircraft bleed air supply. Resulting adverse effects are occurring and creating a risk to flight safety. There is a gap between the aircraft certification requirements for the provision of clean air in crew and passenger compartments using the bleed air system and the documented theoretical and practical implementation of the requirements. Key conclusions include:

1. *Regulations and standards:* Low-level oil leakage over the bearing seals into the bleed air is an expected normal condition at various phases of flight. The required bleed air quality is not being met, as the standards and compliance material are not specific enough to ensure suitable bleed air quality, or application. The focus is placed almost entirely on the prevention of incapacitation, while ignoring impairment, with the clean air requirements open to interpretation.
2. *Design:* Although many suggest the certification requirements for clean air supplies are being met, careful review and research shows this not to be the case. Oil leakage past the bearing seals associated with impaired or degraded performance occurs more frequently than the 'major' remote or improbable regulatory and compliance criteria allow. Oil leakage associated with impairment is probable or above and

is an 'unsafe condition.'

3. *Compliance:* The lack of detection systems to identify the air quality in flight causes ongoing compliance problems. Additionally, the ventilation requirements are not specific enough to ensure occupants will remain free of adverse effects.
4. *Preventative control measures:* Low-level and transient oil emissions are not adequately taken into account when considering acceptable leakage levels. The designs are based on steady state conditions, there are no filtration or detection systems to identify and prevent exposure with rigorous controls lacking.
5. *Retrospectively:* Previous certification requirements were not specific enough to prevent oil leakage into the air supply.
6. *Expertise and communication:* Oil contamination of the air supply is a highly specialist area, with inadequate communication between all relevant parties to ensure compliance and airworthiness.

Recommendations

- Review of standards and guidance material;
- Preventative measures: Normal and abnormal operations: detection systems and flight deck warning, filtration.
- Oil leakage not to be related to rare failure conditions or maintenance factors only;
- Frequency of oil leakage explained by design factor;
- Retrospective certification for bleed air quality;
- Future aircraft – Bleed free designs;
- Far greater emphasis placed on the clean air regulator compliance including low-level oil emissions in normal flight.

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